

Reaction of wetland rice cultivars to dirty panicle disease and the influence of fertilization on the disease. Badeggi, Nigeria, 1979 wet season.

Fertilizer	Reaction to dirty panicle disease ^a					
	SML140-10	MAS2401	FARO15	IR8	IR20	Mean
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	2.5	5.5	1.5	1.5	3.5	2.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₀	2.5	3.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	2.5	8.5	1.5	3.5	2.5	3.7
N ₁₂₀ P ₃₀ + 30K ₆₀	2.5	8.5	5.5	1.5	1.5	3.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₃₀ + 30	3.5	5.5	2.5	1.5	3.5	3.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₃₀ + 30K ₃₀ + 30	5.5	4.5	2.5	1.5	4.5	3.7
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Zn ^b	2.5	4.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.5
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + lime ^c	2.5	3.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + ash ^d	2.5	3.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Mg ^e	1.5	2.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	1.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Si ^f	1.5	2.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	1.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Zn + Mg + Si	2.5	2.5	2.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
Mean	2.8	4.6	2.1	1.7	2.8	

^a 1-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately susceptible, 7-9 = susceptible. ^b 2% ZnO as zinc sulfate. ^c 5 t slaked lime/ha. ^d 5 t straw ash/ha. ^e 40 kg MgO/ha as magnesium sulfate. ^f 80 kg SiO₂/ha as sodium metasilicate.

was susceptible. Unbalanced fertilization (application of NPK only) increased disease incidence in resistant, moderately susceptible, and susceptible cultivars; however, liming or application of straw ash or Mg or Si (in addition to NPK) reduced the disease incidence significantly

in all cultivars (see table).

Isolations from infected panicles suggest that the primary causal organisms of dirty panicle disease are *Curvularia* spp., particularly *C. lunata*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and *Nigrospora* spp. (most prevalent in susceptible cultivars). ■

Ecology of the rice sheath blight pathogen: parasitic survival

T. W. Mew, plant pathologist; N. G. Fabellar, research aide; and F. A. Elazegui, senior research assistant, International Rice Research Institute

The host range of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, the rice sheath blight pathogen, is wide and includes many weed species. In an initial field experiment with direct-seeded and unweeded IR36, both rice and weeds

became infected when the inoculum of the fungus was broadcast on the field. Many weed species including *Echinochloa colona*, *E. glabrescens*, *E. crus-galli* ssp. *hispidula*, and *Monochoria vaginalis* were as susceptible as rice. A subsequent survey of the IRRI farm showed many weeds of the Gramineae family in the rice fields naturally infected with the rice sheath blight pathogen (see table). The symptoms were identical to those on rice. In fallow or idle fields under wetland conditions, sclerotial bodies and

Some weed hosts of sheath blight organism at IRRI, 1979.

Species name	Family	Plant part isolated	Where collected
<i>Chloris</i> sp.	Gramineae	Sheath	Dryland
<i>Cleome rutidosperma</i>	Capparidaceae	Leaf, pod, seed	Wetland
<i>Digitaria</i> sp.	Gramineae	Blade	Wetland
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	Gramineae	Blade sheath	Wetland Dryland
<i>E. crus-galli</i> ssp. <i>hispidula</i>	Gramineae	Sheath	Wetland
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	Gramineae	Sheath	Wetland
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	Pontederiaceae	Leaf	Wetland
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i>	Gramineae	Sheath	Wetland
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Gramineae	Blade, sheath	Wetland
<i>Rottboellia exaltata</i>	Gramineae	Blade	Dryland
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Gramineae	Blade	Dryland

sometimes the basial stage of the fungus could be observed on those weeds. A pathogenicity test of isolates obtained from the weeds suggested that they were highly virulent to rice. These weeds obviously are not only hosts for the fungus but also and, perhaps more important, the source of inoculum to infect the rice crop. ■

A theoretical model for ufra control

P. G. Cox, plant pathologist, BRRI/Office of Development Agency Deepwater Rice Pest Management Project, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

Cox and Rahman have suggested that ufra disease of deepwater rice in Bangladesh, caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev, might be controlled by any procedure that prolongs the overwinter decay phase of the nematode population in infested crop residues left in the field from the previous season. Such methods include the sowing of early maturing varieties (even though they might have to be harvested from a boat), late sowing (risking early flood damage), or transplanting after the floods arrive (if floodwaters do not rise too quickly). A cost is clearly associated with each procedure. The optimum extension of the decay phase will be determined by a trade-off between the yield gain through pest control and the yield loss associated with adoption of the procedure, even in the absence of any disease (see figure).

The function $Y' = f(t)$ shows the potential yield that might be expected in the absence of disease as a result of postponing the time of sowing or transplanting. The yield falls off as the ground becomes too wet for sowing (even using pregerminated seed), or as the water becomes too deep for transplanting or, in shallow situations, as flowering time approaches. The function $Y'' = f(t)$ shows how the potential yield increases, in the absence of physiological losses, as the time of sowing or transplanting is postponed as a result of ufra control through prolongation of the overwinter decay phase. If the crop technology is